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Depression in spinal cord injured patients

Amir.A.Hussain

Abstract

Background: Physical illness is one of the etiological factors in mental illness. The physically disabling conditions, including spinal cord injury, are frequently accompanied by significant psychological conditions.

Spinal cord injury results in alteration and/ or losses of bodily functions, family and social relationships, vocation, and future plans, imposes unusual psychological efforts for coping to the new situations.

Depressed mood and depression are common psychological reactions that are accompanied the changes by spinal cord injury, may be prolonged and severe. Knowing the factors that play a role in establishment of depression in such patients, and the high risk group who are more prone to depression is an essential issue. Early detection of depression may assists in identification of factors that help adjustment and prevention of maladaptation.

Objectives: To determine the prevalence of depression in spinal cord injured patients and its severity and correlation with some sociodemographic variables.

Methods: In a study of 52 patients with spinal cord injury carried out in Abdullah Ibn Maktoom centre for spinal cord injuries and rehabilitation in Baghdad from May to September 1997. The diagnosis of depression was approached via clinical examination, interview and the application of DSMIII-R criteria for depression. The severity of depressive

state was determined by applying the Beck Depression Inventory scale. SPSS (8.0) has been used for descriptive and inferential statistical analysis.

Results:

Fifty-two patients, age range from 22-60 years were studied. The mean age \pm standard deviation was 35.6 ± 6.6 .

The results were that 45 (86.5%) of the patients were depressed, 14 (26.9%) had severe depression and 25(48.1%) were moderate and 6(11.5%) scored mild depression. while 7 (13.5%) patient were non-depressed.

Statistical analysis showed that age, marital status, educational level, type of the military service, and duration of the injury were significantly associated with depression. While previous personal history of depression, family history of depression, pressure bed sores, alcohol and drug abuse although present but were not approaching to a significant level.

Conclusion: The study shows that more than three quarters of spinal cord injured patients had significant depression with varying severities, which denoted that this is a major problem that needs focusing and treatment to prevent the complication and sequels aiming for healthy coping and adjustment with this major disability..

Key word: Depression, Spinal cord injury, Rehabilitation centre, Baghdad

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Introduction

World Health Organization (WHO) defines impairment as an abnormality in body structure, appearance, or organ or system function resulting from any cause [1].

Spinal cord injury (SCI) represents a catastrophic interruption and alteration not only in physical functioning but psychological functioning as well, that affect rehabilitation potentials and the opportunity of returning to previous, familiar social life and work [2,3].

Since World War II, numerous clinicians have attempted to characterize the psychological adjustment of persons who incur a spinal cord injury and to explain how and why the typical patient reacts the way he or she does [4].

Spinal cord injury may produce both immediate and long term stress. Mood disturbances are common among individuals with chronic health condition including SCI or impairment. The commonest psychological response to physical illness is affective reaction, in particular higher level of anxiety and depression were found in individuals with SCI. Anxiety is the immediate response, while depression tends to be a later development. [4, 5].

Some consider depressed mood is to be inevitable lowered mood may be a normal or understandable response to SCI, may be part of normal grief, or may be indicative of a depressive illness. [2, 4].

Depression can have devastating effects on an individual with a SCI in addition to the presence of ulcers and urinary tract infections, compromised immune function, increased hospital stays,

increased medical expenses, decreased social integration, compromised intimate relationships, ability to control voluntary

movement may be compromised, sensation may be affected, bladder and bowel movements may be uncontrolled, and sexual functioning may change and strained caregiver support. [6].

The assessment, diagnosis, and treatment of depression in people with SCI are multilayered processes, complicated by interplay of biological, psychological, strategies aimed at strengthening an individual's social support system [8].

According to the grief model, as described by Hohman [7], resolution of denial is followed by depression. This may be manifested as withdrawal and internalized hostility. The patient may express suicidal ideation. Feeling of futility, lack of motivation and feelings of guilt and uselessness may be severe. The patient may attempt to dissociate himself from the family, married patients may suggest divorce, may be hostile and demanding... Later, hostility may be externalized onto those around the patient, doctors, family and friends may be blamed for the injury Physical and verbal aggression may be prominent. Various authors have characterized depression among SCI patients as internalized anger, sadness over loss, loss of reinforcers, learned helplessness, and result of biochemical changes [9]

Veterans had significantly higher global stress scores than non-veterans with SCI and the general population. Veterans with spinal cord injury have more stress than civilians with spinal cord injury and general population. Veterans with more hassles and more perceived stress were

likely to have more depressive symptoms and anxiety and were less satisfied with themselves [10].

The depressed SCI patient may reject rehabilitation and assistance. Pre-injury personality and means of coping with stress become prominent and intensification of pre-injury traits may be evident. [11].

Depression may vary from mild sadness to extremes of suicide. Suicide and self-neglect are not uncommon long term problems. Follow-up studies have shown 50% of patients with SCI describe suicidal thoughts with depressive mood [12]. The suicide rate for the disabled is greater than that for general population [11]. Suicidal plans during the chronic period may be related to a depressive disorder provoked by prolonged severe impairment [13].

This study was carried out to estimate the prevalence and severity of depression among SCI patients. We also aimed to assess factors that are associated with depression among patients with SCI at Abdulla-Ibn-Maktoom SCI treatment / rehabilitation centre in Baghdad.

Method

This was a cross-sectional study of fifty-two SCI patients at Abdullah Ibn-Maktoom SCI rehabilitation and treatment centre in Baghdad during the period May-September 1997. The patients are interviewed and the sociodemographic information collected. Willingness to participate in the study was obtained by signing a consent form. The diagnosis of depression was made according to a semi-structured interview schedule based on DSMIII R criteria of

depression (American psychiatric association 1988) [14].

The severity of depression was determined by applying the 13-item short form Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), which is Arabic concise version of BDI [15].

The 13-item short form of (BDI) is a test presented in multiple choice format which measures presence and degree of depression. It is a series of questions developed to measure the intensity, severity, and depth of depression in patients with psychiatric diagnoses. It is composed of 13 questions or items, each with four possible responses. Each response is assigned a score ranging from zero to three, indicating the severity of the symptom. The sum of all item scores indicates the severity of depression. Scores from 0-4 indicate no or minimal depressive symptoms, scores of 5-7 indicate mild depression, scores of 8-15 indicate moderate depression and scores of 16 and above indicate severe depression. Individual questions of this form assess mood, pessimism, sense of failure, self-dissatisfaction, guilt, punishment, self-dislike, self-accusation, suicidal ideas, crying, irritability, social withdrawal, body image, work difficulties, insomnia, fatigue, appetite, weight loss, bodily preoccupation, and loss of libido.

Results

The 52 patients participated in the study ranged in age from 22 to 60 years (mean 35.6 and standard deviation 6.6), all were males and paraplegics (as this rehabilitation centre was advocated for military persons only and no females were present).

Forty-five of SCI patients (86.5%) were depressed, while 7 (13.5%) were non-depressed according to DSMII R depressive criteria. table (1). The severity of depression has been shown in table (2).

Table (1): demonstration of frequency of depression in SCI patients

SCI patients		
	Observed N	
Depressed	45	86.5
Non-depressed	7	13.4
Total	52	100.00

DF=1 p< 0.001

Table (2) :Severity of depression.

Valid	Non depressed	Frequency	%	V. %
Depressed	mild	6	11.5	11.5
	moderate	25	48.1	48.1
	severe	14	26.9	26.9
	Total	52	100.0	100.0

The majority (53.8%) were in the age group (30-39) years. Forty-eight percent of them were depressed statistically significant, while 5.7% were non-depressed.

Forty- six percent of depressed patients were single. Depression was higher significantly in unmarried patients. (P< 0.05).

And 23% of them were military voluntaries (professional). Twenty-five percent of them have 11-15 years duration of the SCI. It has been notified that 48% of the sample were conscripts soldiers and depressed. The depression was significantly prevalent among conscripts patients. P value was< 0.05.

Twenty-seven percent of moderately depressed patients were of primary school educational level. 59.6% depressed patients were of primary school educational level. Depression was found in low educational level (primary) in a significant value(P< 0.05).

Depressed SCI patients of 11-15 years duration were 42.3% of the sample.

The period of the injury was significantly related with depression (P< 0.05).

Bedsore and depression were not significant correlated, although presence of 13(25%) depressed with bed sore out of 45 depressed patients. (P value > 0.05.) Six SCI patients (11. 5%) were depressed and abusing alcohol. alcohol and depression were not correlated significantly (p> 0.05).

Twenty-nine percent of depressed patients were drug abusers, while 1%was drug abuser but had no depression. Despite 15 of depressive patients (28.8) were abusing drugs but the 30 patients (57.6) were not so. (P> 0.05) .This is meant that not reaching the significant level. Three (5.7) of depressed SCI patients had previous history of depression prior to injury. Previous history of depression was non significant. (P> 0.05). One depressed SCI patient (1.9) had family history of depressive disorder. Family history of depression was non- significant. (P> 0.05).

Table 4: Statistical significant of the variables between depressed and non-depressed groups:

Variables	Depressed N (%)	Non-depressed N (%)	P value
Age 20-29ys	7 (13.7)	2 (3.8)	Df=5 p<0.05(S)
30-39	25(48.0)	3 (5.7)	
40 and over	13(25.0)	2 (3.8)	
Marital status			Df=4 p<0.05(S)
Single	24 ((46.1)	4 (7.6)	
Married divorced	19 (36.5) 2 (3.8)	3(5.7)	
Educational level			Df=4 p< 0.05(S)
Primary			
Secondary university	31(59.6) 5(9.6) 9(17.3)	3(5.7) 4(7.6)	
Type of military service			Df=4 p<0.05(S)
Conscript			
Reservist Volunteer	26(48.0) 15(28.8) 4(7.6)	5(9.6) 2(3.8)	
Duration of the injury			Df=6 p< 0.05(S)
1-5ys			
6-10	1(1.9)	
11-15 16-20	17(32.6) 22(42.3) 5(9.6)	4(7.6) 2(3.8) 1(1.9)	
Previous history of depression			Df=1 p>0.05(NS)
Positive Negative	3(5.7) 49(94.2)		
Family history of depression			Df=1 p>0.05(NS)
Positive Negative	1(1.9) 51(98.0)		
Bed sores			Df=3 p>0.05(NS)
Present Absent	13(25.0) 32(61.5)	1(1.9) 6(11.5)	
Alcohol abuse			Df=2 p>0.05(NS)
Positive Negative	6(11.5) 39(75.0) 7(13.4)	
Drug abuse			Df=3 p>0.05(NS)
Positive Negative	15(28.8) 30(57.6)	1(1.9) 6(11.5)	

S=significant NS= non-significant

Table (3) Sociodemographic characteristics of the sample

Level of depression	Depressed patients						Non-depressed			
	severe	%	moderate	%	mild	%	Non-depressed	%	total	%
No.	14	26.8	25	48	6	11.5	7	13.5	52	100
Age groups(years)	20-29. 3	5.7	20-29 2	3.8	20-29 2	3.8	20-29 2	3.8	9	17.3
	30-39. 9	17.3	30-39 13	25.0	30-39 3	5.7	30-39 3	5.7	28	53.8
	≥ 40 2	3.8	≥40 10	19.2	≥ 40 1	1.9	≥ 40 2	3.8	15	28.8
Marital status	Married 5	9.6	10	19.2	3	5.7	3	5.7	21	40.3
	Single 7	13.4	15	28.8	3	5.7	4	7.6	29	55.7
	Divorced 2	3.8	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	2	3.8
Military service type	Conscript 8	15.3	14	26.9	4	7.6	5	9.6	31	59.6
	Reservist 4	7.6	10	19.2	1	1.9	2	3.8	17	32.6
	Volunteer 2	7.6	1	1.9	1	1.9	--	----	4	7.6
Duration of injury in years	1-5ys. 1	1.9	---	---	---	---	---	---	1	1.9
	6-10 ys 3	5.7	9	17.3	4	7.6	4	7.6	20	38.4
	11-15 ys 9	17.3	12	23.0	2	3.8	2	3.8	25	48.0
	16-20ys 1	1.9	4	7.6	---	---	1	1.9	6	11.5
Educational level	Primary 12	25	15 4	26.9	4	7.6	3	5.7	34	65.3
	Secondary	-----	6	7.6	1	1.9	2	3.8	7	13.4
	University 2	3.8		11.5	1	1.9	2	3.8	11	21.1
Presence of bed sore	5	9.6	7	13.4	1	1.9	6	11.5	19	36.5
Alcohol abuse	2	3.8	4	7.6	-----	-----	-----	-----	6	11.5
Drug abuse	8	15.3	6	11.5	1	1.9	1	1.9	16	30
Previous history of depression	3	5.7	-----		-----		-----		3	5.7
Family history of depression	1	1.9	-----		-----		-----		1	1.9

Discussion

A review of studies was done to determine the occurrence of depression in SCI persons show different rates, from 0 to 100 percent [16,17,18,19,20,].it is quite variable from study to study, depending on the type of measure, the definition of depression, and whether the taken during rehabilitation, shortly after, ,or somewhat later. Also this variability as resulting from the wide variety of instruments used, from staff ratings, and whether or not a correction for somatic symptoms resulting from the SCI itself was used. Depressive disorders are the most common form of psychological distress in SCI and appears to be more common than in non-disabled population.[21].

The incidence of depressive disorders is higher than in general population (3-10%) and higher than the incidence of depression in orthopedic patients (10-15%) [17]. While in stroke depression was reported in Iraqi study as 66 % of the patients [23].

The results of this study was, 86% (n=45) of SCI patients were depressed out of the total sample fifty-two. Three (5.7%) of the sample have previous history of depression.

Five (22.7%) of SCI patients were depressed after the injury as depression was not exist prior to injury, but developed after the injury and 3% of them were depressed prior to injury [24, 25]. Two of the depressed SCI patients (6.6%) had positive previous history of depression and [26].Which is not so far from the result of our study (5.7%), while 2 SCI depressed patients had positive family history of depression[26]

In this study only minority, one patient, had pervious family history of depression, which meant that the effect of the injury have major role in the etiology of depressive disorder, in addition of the small number of the sample. The previous history of depression was obtained from the past records and from the relatives of the patients and from previous treatments and so the family history of depressive disorders.

This study showed that more than 60% of patients were between 20-39 years.

The mean age appears ranging from 32-50 years, which represent the main economic and social fabric of the community [27, 28, 29, 32]

Various studies have shown that SCI is more common in males than females. Epidemiological studies of SCI in both developed and developing countries have consistently shown reported male: female ratios of between 3:1 and 8.3:1[27, 30].

The sample in this study was male only because this centre is advocated for military persons who didn't involve females.

Some studies showed that SCI is higher among divorced, separated or single and 32% of patients were married [25, 27]. Another studies showed that married and those aged 30-39ys SCI patients are more depressed than others [29, 32].

While in this study 46% was married due to small number of the sample, in addition all of them were military and their injury was due the war.

Drinking problems have been found to be common among medical and surgical ward patients [30, 31]. In which such

drinking problems occur in 20-25% of male ward patients, which has not been appreciated by most physicians.

In this study 11.5% were of alcohol abuse, and when correlated with depression it doesn't reach the significant level. Seven percent of the moderately depressed patients were alcohol dependent, while 2% of severely depressed patients were alcoholic.

In this study the most drugs abused was diazepam and analgesics.

Problems resulting from substance use were reported by 70%; more than half (52%) the sample reported problems during this post- injury period [33].

While these problems (alcohol and drugs) can be a sequel in some SCI patients, they can be significant causes of the injury with their adverse effects on coping and rehabilitation of the injured patients. It has been reported that alcohol and drug abuse were prior to injury and continue after it. [9, 30, 31].

These patients are also at risk of substance abuse after discharge as means of tolerability. Frequent prescribing medications lead to addiction, or large quantities of alcohol or narcotics as part of suicidal tendencies.

The suicide rate for the disabled person is greater than that for general population, and the more the severity of the disability the high rate of suicide [32]. Twelve per cent of U S veterans with traumatic spinal injuries during the period 1946-1965 died by suicide and most suicides occurred within the first five years of injury. Older and unmarried individuals were most at risk [13].

Patients with SCI who are unmarried, beyond age 45 years, with history of alcohol or drug abuse, are the more patients at risk of suicide. Over a half of patients died by suicide were depressed [30].

Paying attention to this problem (depression) will decrease the mortality rate. A gain the SCI can be the result. Nine percent of SCI resulted from attempted suicide [31].

Pressure sores in patients with SCI which throw them in serious medical complications, are highly associated with low self esteem, isolation, depressive mood and held high risk of suicide [34]. The results of this study showed that 25% of SCI depressed patients were with pressure sore.

Also, depression is seen in a new light: as a contributing factor to pressure sores, the most expensive of complications after SCI [32,33].

The limitations of this study were; the small number of the sample and in specific group of population (military males).It had been carried out in 1997 and might not consistent with the current situation. the application of the self-report scale had some misunderstanding ,although the diagnoses of depression was confirmed by the clinical interview and the semi-structural criteria of depressive disorder as mentioned above, add the mixing somatic and psychological symptoms in such patients might over diagnose the depression.

Therefore, screening for and diagnosing depression in those groups of patients is highly reasonable for its potential complex and risk sequels aiming to

reach appropriate management and adjustment

Conclusion and recommendation

Sudden transaction or severe injury to the spinal cord, which disrupts the psychophysical entity of the person, is a major cause of depression that occurs in SCI patients at greater rate than in general population, and other disabilities like orthopedics and stroke.

Furthermore, it is indicated that this group of patients (SCI depressed) can be identified by systematic evaluation using conventional interview and rating scales, and that such patients do respond to treatment with antidepressants medication and other psychosocial measures and identifying some risk factors associated with depression, like those with a pre-injury history of depression, a history of substance abuse, permanent neurological deficit, educational background, social standing, profession, age, as well as the severity and duration of the paralysis were found to be essential factors

Suicide risk assessment is recommended and referral to mental health care services is appropriate. Suicide and self-neglect may be the consequences of unrecognized and untreated depressive illness, suggesting the importance of close monitoring.

Substance-use patterns in persons with SCI who are prescribed with sedating or narcotic medications. Assessment of problems related to substance use and provision of treatment services to persons with traumatic injury are indicated to prevent a potential dual disability.

Also looking for the specific stressors often found with persons with SCI such as inadequate housing, poverty-level income, or family dissolution, are common conditions of handicap that result from the impairment of SCI. A holistic approach to the person with the co-existence of SCI and depression and their additive effect on disability and handicap is required.

Furthermore studies to confirm and extend these findings are indicated.

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